

Scenario modelling for assessing impacts of policy changes and socio-economic effects on ecosystem services of soils

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ABSTRACT

In this study, the impact of an adjustment in the composition of cattle feed on the soil organic carbon stocks in Flanders (Belgium) was investigated. Silage maize is the most common fodder crop, and even the most common crop cultivated in Flanders. However, silage maize does not have a high contribution to the SOC storage in arable soils compared to some other crops, such as cereals and fodder legumes. In this study, we have investigated the impact on SOC stocks of replacing silage maize by winter barley, with straw residues removed after harvest, on 10% of the parcels where it is currently cultivated. The impact of the shift in fodder crops was simulated with a Roth-C based model. The Belgian Soil Organic Carbon Calculator (BeSOCC) integrates the Roth-C model, with an approach for the initialisation and the calculation of carbon inputs by crops and fertilization developed specifically for Belgium, Flanders that builds further on earlier work for developing a digital decision support tool for farmers to simulate the evolution of the SOC in arable land. The scenario was compared with a business-as-usual (BAU) scenario. The BAU scenario was developed based on the management data of 5 years (2018-2022). Due to missing crop and fertilization data, simulations could be performed for 52.3% of the arable fields. The simulations were performed at parcel-level and afterwards aggregated to NUTS3 level. The results indicate that an increase of the SOC storage will occur in all NUTS3 areas if there is a shift in the fodder crops. This increase is on average $0.013 \text{ Mg C. ha}^{-1} \text{ Yr}^{-1}$ and ranges between 0.003 and $0.025 \text{ Mg C. ha}^{-1} \text{ Yr}^{-1}$.

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List of acronyms and abbreviations

SOC	Soil Organic Carbon
BeSOCC	Belgian Soil Organic Carbon Calculator
DPM	Decomposable Plant Material
RPM	Resistant Plant Material
HUM	Humified Organic Matter
BIO	Microbial Biomass
IOM	Inert Organic Matter
BAU	Business-as-usual

1. Introduction

In Flanders, after grass, silage maize is the most important component in the feed composition on many livestock farms and the most common fodder crop used as a basis for cattle feed (ILVO, 2024). It is also the most cultivated crop in Flanders' arable fields. It is cultivated in more than 11000 farms occupying an area of about 120 000 ha (Agentschap Landbouw en Zeevisserij^a, 2024). In Flanders forage maize is a high-energy, high-starch, low-protein forage crop, commonly used for cattle, often in combination with complementary high protein crops like alfalfa. The adoption of silage maize is rising because of its high energy content and easy digestibility among ruminants. However, despite its numerous advantages, silage maize has a limited capacity to contribute to soil organic carbon (SOC) storage compared to other crops (Kan et al., 2022).

SOC storage is important for maintaining soil health and increasing the SOC stocks could aid in the mitigation of climate change by sequestering additional carbon. Replacing silage maize by another fodder crop could lead to an improvement of the SOC storage.

However, completely replacing silage maize is impractical for many farmers, who rely on it as a staple forage crop. Therefore, this study examines a more realistic approach to enhancing SOC storage by replacing silage maize with winter barley on 10% of the parcels currently dedicated to it. To assess the impact of this partial shift on SOC stocks evolution in Flanders, we used a Roth-C-based model.

2. Methodology

To estimate the impact of an adjustment in composition of cattle feed, a scenario was developed to simulate a shift in fodder crops cultivated in Flanders. The scenario was then simulated with a Roth-C based model developed specifically for Flanders (BeSOCC) and compared to a baseline scenario.

2.1. BeSOCC model

The Belgian Soil Organic Carbon Calculator (BeSOCC) integrates the Roth-C model, with an approach for the initialisation and the calculation of carbon inputs by crops and fertilization developed specifically for Belgium, Flanders and builds further on earlier work for developing a digital decision support tool for farmers to simulate the evolution of the SOC in arable fields (Beirinckx et al. 2023; UGent and BDB, 2006; Verlinden et al., 2013). The Roth-C model is a model that simulates the turnover of organic carbon in the top-layer of non-saturated mineral soils (Coleman and Jenkinson, 2014). The model considers different parameters, such as clay content, temperature, monthly rainfall, soil cover and carbon input by crops and organic amendments to calculate the SOC stock. The model divides the SOC stock in four active pools (i.e., DPM, RPM, BIO and HUM) and one inactive pool (i.e., IOM). Each active pool decomposes according to a first-order process with their own characteristic rates. The incoming carbon from organic fertilization and plants are divided over the DPM and RPM pools. The division is based on the DPM/RPM ratio which gives an estimation of the decomposability of the incoming organic matter.

At initialization the BeSOCC model uses the parcel history to distribute the initial SOC stock over the DPM, RPM, BIO and HUM pool (Table 1).

Table 1: Parcel history and associated division of the organic carbon stocks over DPM, RPM, BIO and HUM compartments in the BeSOCC model.

Parcel history	%OC in DPM	%OC in RPM	%OC in BIO	%OC in HUM
Recently torn (< 6 years ago) permanent grassland	1	47	1	51
Arable field	1	15.5	1.5	82

In the BeSOCC model the incoming C coming from crop residues (including roots and exudates) and organic fertilizers is calculated using look-up tables where each crop and fertilizer type is linked to a specific C-content and DPM/RPM ratio. The look-up table for the crops was recently updated by Maenhout et al. (in preparation) and is also used for the local CAP eco-schemes. In the list each crop is assigned a specific C-content value a crop supplies to the soil based on findings from field experiments, expert knowledge or allometric functions. The DPM/RPM ratios were calculated based on the method of Dechow et al. (2019). The list was extended to include more crop types cultivated in Flanders by assigning crops with no values to similar crops that do have a value in the study by Maenhout et al. (In preparation). The look-up table for crops can be found on Zenodo ([10.5281/zenodo.13929423](https://zenodo.org/record/105281/files/zenodo.13929423)).

The look-up table for the fertilizers was first developed by the University of Ghent and soil service of Belgium (Ugent and BDB, 2006) and later updated and extended by the University of Ghent and Flemish Land Agency (Verlinden et al., 2013). Similar as for the crops, the look-up table for the organic fertilizers links the fertilizer type to a C-content, DPM/RPM ratio and a percentage of organic C going directly into the HUM pool. The look-up table for the organic fertilizers can be found on Zenodo ([10.5281/zenodo.13988649](https://zenodo.org/record/105281/files/zenodo.13988649)).

The soil data required for the Roth-C model is the clay content and basic bulk density. The basic bulk density (kg dm^{-3}) is the mass of soil per volume unit under the hypothetical conditions that the SOC would be 0%. The clay content and basic bulk density are used for the initialisation of the SOC stock distribution over the Roth-C pools and for the decomposition of SOC stock in the active Roth-C compartments. The BeSOCC model uses a look-up table to derive these input parameters from the texture class (Table 2). This table was developed by a study by Sleutel et al. , 2006.

Table 2: Clay content (clay%) and basic bulk density (SG_b) (at SOC of 0%) for each texture class as used in the BeSOCC model (Sleutel et al. 2006).

Main texture class	Average clay percentage (%)	Average SG _b (kg dm^{-3})
Sand	4,7	1,55
Sandy loam	9,0	1,33
Loam	14,0	1,40
Clay	23,9	1,40

2.2. Baseline scenario

For the baseline scenario, business-as-usual (BAU) management practices were simulated for each arable field in Flanders. To develop the BAU scenario the crop rotation and fertilization of the 2018-2022 period, obtained from the LPIS data (Agentschap Landbouw en Zeevisserij^b, 2024) and the fertilization allocation model (BAM; Van Opstal et al. 2014) respectively.

The LPIS data contain the crops and cover crops cultivated on each agricultural parcel each year, as well as information that indicates if a field is recently (< 6 years) converted from permanent grassland. The boundaries of agricultural parcels can change every year. For the baseline scenario the field boundaries of 2022 were chosen and for the years 2018-2021 the dominant crops within these boundaries were selected. The LPIS data do not contain information on the straw removal after harvest of a crop. Thus, in the baseline scenario it was assumed that for all cereals the straw residues are removed after harvest. The crops' sowing and harvesting month are required for a simulation with the BeSOCC model. A look-up table with each crops' sowing and harvesting months was developed for Flanders' crops by combining data required from the Agency of Agriculture and Fisheries and studies by Verlinden et al. (2013) (Demeter) and Cecelja et al. (2019) (C-factor studie) (**10.5281/zenodo.13929370**).

The fertilization allocation model (BAM) was developed by the Flemish Environment Agency. The model considers the total amount of fertilizer used per farm and per year and the crops at plot level and based on expert rules make a rational estimate of the amount and type of fertilizer applied to each plot, as well as the time of application. It considers the available information on fertilizer production, fertilizer use, fertilizer transport and fertilizer storage at farm level, as well as the fertilization standards. (Van Opstal et al. 2014 and VMM 2016). The data obtained from the BAM model contains many fertilization applications with a dose of less than 1 Mg fertilizer/ha. A threshold for the dose of fertilizer was set at 1 Mg/ha, since this is an unrealistically low dose for organic fertilizers.

The soil data was obtained from map layers available by the (sub)soil database of Flanders (DOV). The initial SOC stocks were obtained from the Soil Organic Carbon Stock Maps for Belgium with a resolution of 40m x 40m (DOV^a, 2024). The texture classes were obtained from the digital soil map of the Flemish region which has a resolution of 1:20 000 (DOV^b, 2024). Based on the selected field boundaries of 2022 the dominant texture class was chosen, and the mean SOC-stock was calculated for each field.

The Roth-C model is unable to perform simulations on waterlogged soils and also our focus is on mineral soils. For the baseline scenario we assumed that, if the SOC is more than 10%, it is considered peat (Tits et al., 2020) and thus assumed to be waterlogged. For that a threshold at 10% was set for the SOC content in the baseline scenario.

The climatological data needed to conduct simulations with the Roth-C model were obtained from the Joint Research Centre (JRC) Agri4Cast dataset (agri4cast.jrc.ec.europa.eu). This database contains daily observations from weather stations interpolated on a 25x25 km grid for the whole of Europe. Flanders' climatological data was derived from this dataset by calculating the daily average rainfall, air temperature and evapotranspiration of the whole region. For all three parameters the monthly averages of 30 years (1992-2021) were calculated and used as input parameters (Table 3).

Table 3: Monthly average climatological data for Flanders as used in the BeSOCC model (derived from Joint Research Centre (JRC) Agri4Cast (agri4cast.jrc.ec.europa.eu)).

Month	Temperature (°C)	Precipitation (mm)	Evapotranspiration (mm)
January	4.06	64.21	15.27
February	4.77	57.19	22.29
March	7.20	49.43	43.74
April	10.24	39.24	72.21
May	13.83	55.25	99.95
June	16.80	62.10	111.51
July	18.72	70.46	114.87
August	18.57	71.99	97.56
September	15.63	60.98	61.72
October	11,88	66.66	35.66
November	7,68	65.09	16.88
December	4,76	74.33	12.77

The 5-year management practices were simulated for each parcel over a period of 30 years. Due to missing C-inputs coming from some crops and fertilizers, simulations could be performed for 52.3% of the arable fields. The Δ SOC-stock ($\text{Mg C. ha}^{-1}. \text{yr}^{-1}$) was calculated for each parcel and then aggregated to a NUTS3-level.

2.3. Cattle feed adjustment scenario

In Flanders, the most common crop is silage maize, covering 37% of the region's arable parcels. However, its contribution to the SOC storage in arable soils is relatively low compared to some other crops, such as fodder legumes and cereals, especially when the straw from these crops is left on the field after harvest (Panagea et al., submitted). In the investigated scenario, we assumed that some farmers will try to improve their soils by diversifying their crop rotation with crops with higher C inputs into the soil. It was decided to use a cereal, and more specifically winter barley as a replacement for silage maize on 10% of the silage maize parcels. Winter barley is a cereal commonly used as a fodder crop.

We assumed that the straw residues of winter barley would be removed from the field after harvest, since this is common practice in Flanders. In the selected parcels the cover crops from the previous year were removed from the rotation as winter barley is normally sown in the previous year and harvested in August. According to Jeangros and Courvoisier (2019), it is not the most beneficial option to sow a cereal after the harvest of winter barley. In this scenario, the assumption was made that if a cereal was declared as an aftercrop after the replaced silage maize in a parcel, it would be removed from the crop rotation. However, if the following year a cereal was declared as main crop in the LPIS data, and thus sown the same year as winter barley's harvest, it was not removed from the rotation. Each year in the five-year crop rotation, all the fields with silage maize were selected for this scenario and from these fields, 10% were randomly selected to replace silage maize by winter barley. This five-year crop rotation was then repeated for a duration of 30 years in the simulation with the BeSOCC model. The selection and simulation with the BeSOCC model was repeated five times. For each field the mean Δ SOC-stock, Δ SOC-stock_{yearly} and SOC accrual of the five repeated simulations was calculated and then aggregated to a NUTS3-level. The Δ SOC-

stock (Mg C. ha^{-1}) is the change in SOC found after 30 years. The $\Delta\text{SOC-stock}_{\text{yearly}}$ ($\text{Mg C. ha}^{-1} \cdot \text{Yr}^{-1}$) is the annual change in SOC and is calculated with the following equation:

$$\Delta\text{SOC stock}_{\text{yearly}} = \frac{\Delta\text{SOC stock}}{30} \quad (1)$$

The SOC accrual ($\text{Mg C. ha}^{-1} \cdot \text{Yr}^{-1}$) gives the annual increase in SOC stock found in the cattle feed adjustment scenario in comparison to the baseline scenario (Don et al. 2023). It can be calculated with the following equation:

$$\text{SOC accrual} = \Delta\text{SOC stock}_{\text{yearly,cattle feed adjustment}} - \Delta\text{SOC stock}_{\text{yearly,baseline}} \quad (2)$$

3. Results and discussion

The simulated BAU scenario resulted in a mean $\Delta\text{SOC-stock}$ of $3.12 \text{ Mg C. ha}^{-1}$ for all of Flanders. This indicates that if the current management practices will continue to be applied for the next 30 years there will be an annual increase in SOC storage of $0.104 \text{ Mg. ha}^{-1} \cdot \text{yr}^{-1}$. However, Figure 1 illustrates that the $\Delta\text{SOC-stock}$ differs between the different NUTS3 regions. In the NUTS3 regions BE256 (District Roeselare) and BE213 (District Turnhout) we expect a decrease in SOC-stocks under BAU, while in BE242 (District Leuven) an increase is expected (Table 4).

Figure 1 : $\Delta\text{SOC-stock}_{\text{yearly}}$ ($\text{Mg C. ha}^{-1} \cdot \text{yr}^{-1}$) per NUTS3 level in Flanders obtained with a simulation with the Business-as-usual scenario.

In the BAU scenario, silage maize is cultivated each year on an average area of 103,635 ha. In the scenario with a shift in fodder crops on average 9,150 ha of this area were replaced by winter barley. This shift in fodder crop rotation resulted in an increase of Flanders' $\Delta\text{SOC-stock}$ of $3.51 \text{ Mg C. ha}^{-1}$ after

30 years. Thus, the scenario gave an annual increase in the SOC storage of $0.013 \text{ Mg C. ha}^{-1} \cdot \text{Yr}^{-1}$ compared to the BAU scenario.

Figure 2: Δ SOC-stocks_{yearly} ($\text{Mg C. ha}^{-1} \cdot \text{yr}^{-1}$) per NUTS3 level in Flanders obtained with simulations with the shift in fodder crop scenario.

However, to obtain a better insight in how and where the Δ SOC-stock differs between the BAU and cattle feed adjustment scenario, the SOC accrual was calculated and mapped (Figure 3 and table 4). The map shows that the NUTS3 region which is most impacted is BE211 (District Antwerp). This region shows an increase of $0.60 \text{ Mg C. ha}^{-1}$. The SOC accrual due to the shift in fodder crops will be $0.025 \text{ Mg C. ha}^{-1} \cdot \text{yr}^{-1}$. In this region 6.7 % of the area cultivated with silage maize in the BAU scenario was replaced by winter barley (Table 4). NUTS3 region BE211 is actually the region where the most silage maize is cultivated in Flanders. Other NUTS3 regions which appear to have the highest SOC accrual by the cattle feed adjustment scenario are BE212 (District Mechelen), BE232 (District Dendermonde), BE213 (District Turnhout) and BE225 (District Maaseik), which are all districts where in more than 50% of the arable fields silage maize is cultivated. Since winter barley is known to have a positive impact on the SOC-stock, it was expected that the regions where silage maize is the most cultivated will be the most impacted by the shift in fodder crops.

Figure 3: The SOC accrual ($\text{Mg C} \cdot \text{ha}^{-1} \cdot \text{yr}^{-1}$) of the shift in fodder crop scenario per NUTS3-level.

The NUTS3 regions least impacted are BE242 (District Leuven) and BE223 (District Tongeren) (Table 4). In these regions 1.8 % and 2.38 % of the area with silage maize was replaced by winter barley. Other NUTS3 regions showing lower SOC accruals are BE241 (District Halle-Vilvoorde), BE235 (District Oudenaarde), BE258 (District Veurne) and BE254 (District Kortrijk). In all of these NUTS3 regions less than 3.5% of the total arable land was replaced by winter barley. Additionally, all these NUTS3 regions have a share of less than 30% of silage maize.

The regions BE253 (District Ieper), BE256 (District Roeselare) and BE235 (District Oudenaarde) have a similar share of 27% area with silage maize (Table 4). However, the SOC accrual in BE235 is $0.004 \text{ Mg C} \cdot \text{ha}^{-1} \cdot \text{yr}^{-1}$ lower than the other two regions. The area replaced by winter barley is around 3% in all three regions. Thus, the lower SOC accrual found in BE235 is not due to the area undergoing a shift in fodder crop. As mentioned in the methodology, cover crops in the year preceding the shift to winter barley are removed from the rotation because winter barley is normally sown the previous year. Cover crops are known to be beneficial for the SOC stock (Poeplau and Don, 2015). Thus, if in region BE235 more cover crops were removed from the rotation in comparison to BE253 and BE256 a lower SOC accrual for BE235 will be found. The ΔSOC -stock in the BAU scenario found for BE235 is one of the highest of all the NUTS3 regions, which indicates that in this region many cover crops are sown, and thus the impact of the cattle feed adjustment scenario will be more limited.

The standard deviation found for the ΔSOC -stock_{yearly} and ΔSOC -stock is similar in each NUTS3 region (Table 4). The standard deviation for both measures indicates that between the five repeated simulations

the effect of the cattle feed adjustment scenario differs. The standard deviation found for the area replaced by winter barley (table 4) is higher for the NUTS3 regions with a high spread for the Δ SOC-stock. This shows that the spread found for Δ SOC-stock in the NUTS3 regions is higher if the area replaced by winter barley varies more between the five repeated simulations, thus showing that the impact of the cattle feed adjustment scenario is influenced by the area replaced by winter barley. However, some NUTS3 regions, such as BE258 and BE236, have lower standard deviations for the area replaced by winter barley but a high standard deviation for the Δ SOC-stock. This indicates that the Δ SOC-stock in the repeated simulations is also influenced by some of the assumptions made in the cattle feed adjustment scenario, such as the removal of cover crops in the preceding year. To conclude, the implementation of the shift in fodder crop scenario always leads to a higher Δ SOC-stock compared to the BAU scenario. The actual increase is, however, also impacted by other management practices such as the inclusion of cover crops.

Table 4: Results of Business-as-usual (BAU) scenario and cattle feed adjustment scenario.

NUTS3		BAU scenario		Cattle feed adjustment scenario				SOC accrual (Mg C. ha ⁻¹ . yr ⁻¹)	Area silage maize / total arable land (%)	Area replaced by winter barley / total arable land (%)	Standard deviation (%)
Code	Name	ΔSOC-stock (Mg C. ha ⁻¹)	ΔSOC- stock _{yearly} (Mg C. ha ⁻¹ . yr ⁻¹)	ΔSOC-stock (Mg C. ha ⁻¹)	Standard deviation (Mg C. ha ⁻¹)	ΔSOC- stock _{yearly} (Mg C. ha ⁻¹ . yr ⁻¹)	Standard deviation (Mg C. ha ⁻¹ . yr ⁻¹)				
BE211	Antwerpen	2.40	0.08	3.00	0.72	0.10	0.02	0.025	60.8	6.7	0.16
BE212	Mechelen	1.50	0.05	2.10	0.69	0.07	0.02	0.020	52.3	5.4	0.20
BE213	Turnhout	-0.60	-0.02	-0.06	0.77	-0.002	0.03	0.022	54.2	5.7	0.10
BE223	Tongeren	6.60	0.22	6.60	0.46	0.22	0.02	0.004	19.3	2.4	0.13
BE224	Hasselt	3.00	0.10	3.60	0.54	0.12	0.02	0.012	35.5	3.7	0.14
BE225	Maaseik	2.40	0.08	3.30	0.74	0.11	0.02	0.022	55.7	5.8	0.18
BE231	Aalst	6.00	0.20	6.30	0.48	0.21	0.02	0.008	32.6	4.2	0.16
BE232	Dendermonde	1.80	0.06	2.40	0.72	0.08	0.02	0.020	52.6	5.5	0.21
BE233	Eeklo	2.40	0.08	3.00	0.73	0.10	0.02	0.017	42.4	4.4	0.11
BE234	Gent	2.70	0.09	3.30	0.72	0.11	0.02	0.019	49.1	5.2	0.10
BE235	Oudenaarde	6.60	0.22	6.60	0.46	0.22	0.02	0.006	27.3	3.2	0.08
BE236	Sint-Niklaas	0.90	0.03	1.20	0.79	0.04	0.03	0.016	40.4	4.1	0.03
BE241	Halle- Vilvoorde	6.60	0.22	6.60	0.48	0.22	0.02	0.005	22.6	2.6	0.07
BE242	Leuven	8.70	0.29	8.70	0.36	0.29	0.01	0.003	13.9	1.8	0.06
BE251	Brugge	1.80	0.06	2.40	0.74	0.08	0.02	0.015	39.7	4.1	0.08
BE252	Diksmuide	1.20	0.04	1.80	0.71	0.06	0.02	0.012	33.9	3.5	0.16
BE253	Ieper	2.70	0.09	3.00	0.67	0.10	0.02	0.010	27.3	3.0	0.04
BE254	Kortrijk	3.90	0.13	3.90	0.57	0.13	0.02	0.008	25.9	3.0	0.13
BE255	Oostende	0.90	0.03	1.20	0.67	0.04	0.02	0.009	24.7	2.7	0.14
BE256	Roeselare	-0.03	-0.001	0.30	0.77	0.01	0.03	0.010	27.1	2.8	0.13
BE257	Tielt	1.50	0.05	2.10	0.76	0.07	0.03	0.015	38.6	4.0	0.13
BE258	Veurne	2.70	0.09	2.70	0.68	0.09	0.02	0.006	17.4	1.8	0.06

Conclusion

The cattle feed adjustment scenario showed that the replacement of silage maize by another fodder crop, which is known to be beneficial for SOC storage, leads to an additional increase or lower loss of the SOC stock in simulations with the BeSOCC model. Even though for the cattle feed adjustment scenario, other management practices for SOC storage, such as straw remaining on the field and inclusion of cover crops, were not implemented an increase in Flanders' SOC stock was found. The impact of the scenario at NUTS3 level is dependent on the area of cultivated silage maize, but also the cover crops cultivated in the preceding year will influence the effect on SOC storage. Further development of this scenario by including cover crops after winter barley's harvest and leaving straw residues on the field could lead to a more beneficial impact on the SOC storage.

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